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Research Article

Role of Development and Accreditation Deanship for Qualification of Hail Faculties, Saudi Arabia for Local Accreditation

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ABSTRACT

Quality education is a prerequisite to gain access to knowledge which guarantees economic development. This makes the condition of higher education in Saudi Arabia a very critical issue. The present work aimed to discuss the quality movement of Hail University, Particularly, the efforts of Deanship of Development and Quality (DQD) in setting up NCAAA standards (National Commission for Academic Accreditation and Assessment). In the process, the authors identify the steps for technical support e.g.: Workshops, Site visits and meetings in addition, design of different action plans for quality assurance activities and accreditation approach. The results revealed that, 90% from Hail Faculties achieved most of DQD requirements except Community and Engineering Faculties.

Keywords: Quality assurance, Accreditation, Hail University, DQD.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education is very essential for active participation in the knowledge of societies which in turn accelerates economic growth. Quality education is a prerequisite to gain access to knowledge which guarantees economic development. This makes the condition of higher education in Pakistan a very critical issue. Recognizing this, the Higher Education Commission is committed to quality assurance and enhancement of higher education institutions. To achieve world class standards, quality assessment and continuous improvement are the necessary ingredients. This includes the accreditation of academic programmes and quality assessment of the university / institution. The university quality assessment is primarily concerned with the institutional issues rather than programme issues [Batool,2000; Lewis,1989; Freeman, 1991; Tait,1993].

Quality Assurance is the planned and systematic review process of an institution or programme to determine whether or not acceptable standards of education, scholarship and infrastructure are being met, maintained and enhanced.¹ It is an instrument designed to add value to higher education by encouraging high quality. An efficient and effective high quality/ higher education system which is internationally recognized and a well established national Quality Culture are vital for economic growth in developing countries like Pakistan. A sustainable quality assurance programme enhances employment opportunities, improves the education and training of future employees, harnesses future leaders, facilitates an enabling learning environment, and enriches the academic and intellectual landscape. Thus it fuels the engine of economic and social development at the national, regional and international levels [Batool,2001].

A quality higher education system is essential to the successful development and functioning of an open and democratic civil society. Higher education is expected to provide the social norms of communication and interaction such as philosophical thinking and reasoning to promote the sovereignty of its individuals, and to eliminate all kinds of social-class ethnic conflicts and gender or Religious biases. A quality providing institution of higher education is a model for creating a modern civil society. This ideal state of academic quality is not commonly realized but it is, nevertheless, a yardstick by which to measure the effectiveness of higher education systems operating in the country [Hodgkin,1994] The development of Quality Assurance is a continuous process and therefore, continuity of strategies, actions and efforts is a prerequisite for quality in higher education. Quality Assurance including its processes, procedures and outcomes of assessment is a challenge and its management is even a greater challenge

to practitioners seeking workable guidelines, evidences of good practices and tools that will facilitate the process [Reid,1992].

National Commission for Academic accreditation and Assessment was the establishment of the Saudi Commission for Assessment and Accreditation based on the approval of the High Commissioner No. 7 / b / 6024 dated 02/09/1424 on the Higher Education Council resolution No. 03/28/1424 at its twenty-eighth held on 15.01.1424, and this body shall enjoy the moral and financial and administrative independence under the supervision of the Board of higher Education which is the authority responsible for the affairs of academic accreditation in higher education institutions Saudi and that the possibility of improving the quality of higher education Saudi (in particular), and to ensure clarity and transparency, and provide standards codified for academic performance.

The National Commission for Academic accreditation and Assessment (NCAAA) in Saudi Arabia are making concerted efforts to improve the quality of higher education and to move university education to meet international standards in the provision of high-quality teaching, learning, research and service. A focused and precise approach is being developed for the best results and for consistency in the process of the Quality Assurance & Enhancement in higher education in the country. It reflects an effort to sensitize higher education institutions to the changes taking place internationally and bring higher education in Saudi Arabia into complete harmony with the shifting paradigms at leading institutions around the world.

University of Hail started as a community college, called Hail Community College (HCC), under the auspices of King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals (KFUPM) in September 1998. HCC was the first Community College to open in a planned expansion of educational opportunities for Saudi Arabian high school graduates. HCC started by offering three-years Associate degree programs in Business Administration, Computer Systems, and Electronics Engineering and Instrumentation. Later on, HCC offered three Bachelor degree programmes in Applied Electrical Engineering, Computer Science, and Management Information Systems.

University of Hail was officially established by Royal Decree on 30 Rabi II, 1426H (7 June 2005). The university consists of ten colleges: College of Medicine & Medical Sciences, College of Sciences, College of Engineering, College of Computer Science & Engineering, and Community College. The first students were admitted on 11 February 2006. In 2007, two existing colleges joined the university, which are Teachers College and Girls Education College. These two colleges were originally under the auspices of the Ministry of Education. The university enrolment has grown to more than 16,000 students. The vision of the University of Hail is to become the first corporate university in the Middle East Region where technology and innovation are the two main elements used to sustain continuous development in the 21st Century. The University of Hail is the University of the Future that moves at "the speed of change".

Deanship of Quality and Development (DQD) as main Deanships in Hail University is Seek deanship to achieve the highest degree of quality in the practice of academic and administrative campus, and through developing the skills of employees of the university, and employees of public and private sectors of society, and the application of quality assurance standards and accreditation within the university and conducting applied studies and planning to support it in achieving its strategic objectives. Visio, mission and main objectives of DQD were presented in Appendix I.

Aim of the present work:

Evaluation the first impact of Development and Quality Deanship activities on promotion of Hail Facilities for continuous improvement and local accreditation

Methods

The achievement of our goals started with design the short action plan (4 Months) from 1\9 to 31\12\ 2012 as shown in Table (1) and Figure 1.

The action plan is divided into 5 main parts: Goals, out puts, Activities, Times, Success indicators.

Figure 1: In-put and Out-put of short action plan

Table 1. Action plane of technical support for 10 faculties (include work shop-site visit-communications) during first semester 2012/2013

Main Goals	Out put	Activities	Duration time	Responsibility	Success indicator
DQD requirements	Faculties Vision and mission	Work shop for preparation of vision and mission	1-30/10/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	Faculties vision and mission
	Data capture form	-Design of data capture form by DQD -Sending the data form to all university faculties	1/9-30/10/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	Capture form with complete data
	Headquarters quality	-Customize the headquarter of quality	1-30/10/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	Headquarter for accreditation activities with all equipments
Promote a culture of quality	Professor with high awareness of quality	-3 Workshop on quality concepts and terminology	1-30/9/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	Increase the quality awareness for academic staff in hail University by 70%
		- 2 Work shop on Strategic plan	1-30/10/2012		
		-3 Workshop on Program specification	1-30/11/2012		
		-3 Work shop on self assessment	1-30/12/2012		
	employments with high awareness of quality	-3 Workshop on quality concepts and terminology	1/10-30/11/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	60% Increase the quality awareness
	Students with high awareness of quality	-Workshop on quality concepts and terminology	1/10-30/11/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	60% Increase the quality awareness
Promotion the faculties for local accreditation	Faculties staff with high awareness with local accreditation standards (NCAAA)	2 Work shop on Accreditation standards	1/10-30/11/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	70% increase the accreditation standards awareness
	Self assessment report	-2 Work shop for all university staff	1-30/11/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	70% increase self assessment awareness
		Site visit for technical support for all faculties	15/11-15/12/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	The level of beneficiaries satisfaction
		Action plan for completion the self assessment process	1-15/12/2012	DQD Quality and Accreditation management	The level of beneficiaries satisfaction

Measurement of performance indicator

Usually we measure the success indicator by the following items:

Questioner

Especially for workshop and training program by beneficiaries (as see in appendix II).

Site visit

The site visits for all faculties started from 15/11/2012 to 15/12/2012 for technical support in different quality assurance fields and the activities for continuous improvement and qualification for local Accreditation from National Commission for Academic Accreditation and Assessment (The site visit program in appendix). The technical support includes the followings topic: Program specification, accreditation benefits, self evaluation, Promote a culture of quality. The site visit program (as see in appendix III). The site visits will be repeated every month for follow up, Technical support and evaluation all quality assurance activities in all faculties.

Follow up the completion of DQD requirements

The DQD requirements from all the University faculties are mentioned as follow:

Vision and mission, Job description, Organization structure, Program specification, action plan for self assessment, Quality committee meeting, Good preparation for site visit, Headquarters quality, Data capture form, Promote a culture of quality. Then, The DQD members were checked for quality to ascertain these requirements or documents and the results were mentioned in Table 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To be accredited, institutions or programs must comply with generally expected standards of good practice. The Commission has defined the standards it will apply in two documents, Standards for Quality Assurance and Accreditation in Higher Education Institutions and Standards for Quality Assurance and Accreditation in Higher Education Programs. Reference is also made to several other documents including a National Qualifications Framework that describes expected general standards of learning outcomes in four domains of learning and a statement showing the application of these standards to distance education programs. Standards for technical training are in preparation. These statements are expressed in general terms applicable to all fields of study. It is also necessary for programs to meet requirements for professional practice in many professional fields. Details of these requirements are not yet available from the Commission [Chea, 2000].

In many countries, however, student are required to pay an increasing proportion of the costs of their study and will no longer behave in a subservient manner, accepting poor service or care from university teachers and administrator. If a modern distance teaching organization is not to produce more drop-outs than graduate, or to lose students to competing institutions, then quality assurance will form an important element in its methods of work. This case study aims to evaluate the DQD activities in Hail University and respond speedily to the different Hail faculties for continuous improvement, in addition, demonstrate that it would be of value to learn more about modern quality assurance system for distance education in an international context.

Deanship of Quality and Development provide both technical and financial support for each faculty in Hail University. From these technical supports, DQD organized more than 25 workshops for all human resources in 10 Hail faculties in different quality assurance and accreditation topics (as shown in Table 1)

The total number of participants reached 550 including male and female and the success indicator was measured by a questioner (as shown in appendix II).

The results present in Figure (2) found that, the level of beneficiaries' satisfaction in all workshops and meeting reached to more than 90%.

The results shown in Table 2 reported that, There are differences in response of Hail faculties to DQD requirements, From the obtained data, we found that, all faculties were prepared well for the first site visit for technical support (Staff members attended, Class room preparation, Evidences for activities) However, All faculties prepared Headquarter for quality activities except faculty of Engineering, In addition, most of the faculties responded to all DQD requirements (e.g.: Organization structure, Vision and Mission, Headquarter, Data captured form, Quality committee meetings, Form a work group) except, Faculty of Engineering and Faculty of Social) However, Only one faculty responded to primary self evaluation and sent the final report to DQD for revision. These results may be due

to the variety of faculty nature. [Crea, 2001; Hämäläinen, 2001]. These phenomena correlated with quality activities and response to DQD requirements and Accreditation standard (appendix VI).

CONCLUSION

This report focuses on higher education accreditation, audits, institutional academic reviews, and other quality assurance activities at the programme, institutional and national levels in Saudi Arabia as a whole. It represents a first effort to map, explore and assess accreditation and audits in higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia as a whole and to focus on several case studies that are illustrative of the process. The information presented here, the assessments, and recommendations are intended to inform and assist those interested in quality assurance in general and suggest approaches and strategies for those contemplating university accreditation, audits and academic reviews.

Figure2. Level of beneficiaries' satisfaction in all quality assurance workshops done by DQD.

Table 2. The response of different Faculties' for DQD requirements

Faculties	Vision and mission	Jop description	Organization structure	Prog. Specification	Primary self Assessment	Quality committee meeting	Good preparation for site visit	Head-quarters quality	Data capture form	Promote a culture of quality	Form a working group for NCAAA standard
Scientific faculties											
A. Med	+++	++	+++	+	-	+++	+++	++	+	+++	+++
B. AMS	++	+	+++	-	-	+++	+++	+++	++	+	+++
C.GHI	+	+	+++	+++	-	+++	+++	+++	++	+	++
D. Sic	+	-	++	-	-	+++	+++	+++	++	+	-
E .Eng	-	-	-	-	-	+++	+++	-	-	-	-
F. Coun	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
G. IT	++	++	+++	-	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+++
H. Nur	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
Theory faculties											
I. Art	+	+	++	-	-	+++	++	+++	+	+	-
J. Edu	+++	++	+++	-	-	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	+

The response speed (low +; medium ++; fast +++)

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Appendixes

Appendix I: Vision, Mission and Strategic objectives of DQD

Vision:

House of distinct experience locally and internationally in the development of skills of employees of the university, and the achievement of total quality standards in all academic and research practices and management to ensure access to academic and institutional accreditation.

Mission:

Seek deanship to achieve the highest degree of quality in the practice of academic and administrative campus, and through developing the skills of employees of the university, and employees of public and private sectors of society, and the application of quality assurance standards and accreditation within the university and conducting applied studies and planning to support it in achieving its strategic objectives.

Strategic Objectives:

The Deanship the development and quality aims at achieve the following strategic objectives:

1. Draw future strategies needed to raise the skills of employees of the university to achieve excellence and innovation in education, teaching and scientific research.
2. Organizational aspects in the development of university administration.
3. Contributing to the Strategic Plan of the University.
4. Assess training needs and staff development for employees of public and private sectors within the community.
5. Measure and evaluate the performance of all elements of the system work at the university.
6. Applying quality assurance and accreditation system for all components of the administrative and academic within the university.
7. Contribute to the development of management and leadership skills for academic and administrative leadership at the university so that they can change the target successfully.
8. Access the university to be a tank contributes to community service through the development of human resource skills of both the public and private sectors in a professional, professional and commercial basis to contribute to increase sources of income to the university.

Appendix II: Questioner**Your feedback is sincerely appreciated**

1=strongly disagree 2=Disagree 3=neither agree nor disagree 4=Agree 5=strongly agree.

WORKSHOP CONTENT						
	Items	Response				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I was well informed about the objectives					
2	This workshop lived up to my expectations					
3	The content is relevant to my job					
WORKSHOP DESIGN						
4	The workshop objectives were clear to me					
5	The workshop activities stimulated my learning					
6	The activities in this workshop gave me sufficient practice					
7	The pace of this workshop was appropriate					
WORKSHOP INSTRUCTOR (FACILITATOR)						
8	The instructor was well prepared					
9	The instructor was helpful.					
WORKSHOP RESULTS						
10	I accomplished the objectives of this workshop.					
11	I will be able to use what I learned in this workshop					

Appendix III:**Site visit program**

Time	Activities	Requirements
10 -10:15 am	Meeting with Academic leader (Dean and Vice dean, Chair depart)	
10:15 – 10:45	Discuss the Program specification stages	the Program specification template
10:45 - 11:15	Discuss the self assessment standard	Template of NCAAA for self assessment
11:15 - 12	Site visit for teaching room, lab and Headquarter room	

Appendix IV:**Standards for Institutions and Standards for Programs (From NCAAA)**

A. Institutional Context

1. Mission and Objectives
2. Governance and Administration
3. Management of Quality Assurance and Improvement

B. Quality of Learning and Teaching

4. Learning and Teaching

C. Support for Student Learning

5. Student Administration and Support Services
6. Learning Resources

D. Supporting Infrastructure

7. Facilities and Equipment
8. Financial Planning and Management
9. Employment Processes

E. Community Contributions

10. Research
11. Institutional Relationships with the Community